

USE OF VISUALISATION TO IMPROVE THE WRITING SKILLS OF STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Many researches has been conducted for the need to increase critical thinking of students (in different fields, also many researches has been done on the importance and the role of critical thinking for students achievements. In this context this requires a critical approach. To achieve this should be used effective teaching methods that develop critical thinking and also facilitate and enhance the learning of students and their performance in general, making them able to solving problems in their fields. A visualization approach increase communication, increase critical thinking and provides analytical approach to various problems. Therefore, this research is aimed to investigate visualization for the purpose of examining its role in developing critical thinking. In order to achieve this it was made an experiment for the use of visualization and from this experimentation are extracted the results of the effect of using the visualization for the aspect of developing and increasing critical thinking. The results which are taken from this research highlight the positive effect that the use of visualization in teaching and learning process has in developing the critical thinking of students and their overall performance. The results also shows that the visualization motivates students to learn, making them more cooperative and developing their skills for critical approach.

Key Words: Visualization, Critical Thinking, Teaching, Learning & Student Performance

Four Skills in Language Learning:

In-order to become a well-rounded communicator one needs to be proficient in each of the four language skills. These four skills give learners opportunities to create contexts in which to use the language for exchange of real information, evidence of their own ability (proof of learning) and, most important, confidence. Listening and reading are the receptive skills because learners do not need to produce language, they receive and understand it. These skills are sometimes known as passive skills. The productive skills are speaking and writing because learners are applying these skills in a need to produce language. They are also known as active skills.

Importance of Writing Skills:

Writing provides a learner with physical evidence of his achievements and he can measure his improvement. It helps to consolidate their grasp of vocabulary and structure, and complements the other language skills. It helps to understand the text and write compositions. It can foster the learner's ability to summarize and to use the language freely. To write flawless language one should excel in the Writing Skills with the help of various methods. Importance should be given to composition and creative writing. One should also focus on coherence and cohesiveness when it comes to writing a language.

Writing is a form of communication and should be shared with others. Students should have the ability to choose what to write about, have ample time to develop ideas, and receive feedback from peers and instructors to write effectively (Atwell, 1987; Routman, 1994; Wood & Dickinson, 2000). Donald Graves (1983/2003) stated young students should publish because, "Publishing contributes strongly to a writer's development" (p. 54). One of the main goals of teachers is to create lifelong writers. To achieve this goal, teachers should provide positive writing experiences in a comfortable learning environment where students feel free to take risks and express themselves (Chambliss & Bass, 1995). When 5 students enter kindergarten they most often do not see themselves as readers, but almost always as writers. Language is the ability to construct meaning from experiences (Tompkins, 2001). From the kindergarten students' perspectives, they can write because, to them, their scribbles and drawings have meaning. To create lifelong writers, teachers should provide opportunities for students to write and express themselves every day. Writing should be seen as a way to record information, write personal notes, share poetry, and stories. Writing should not be produced in isolation, but integrated in every subject. Using writing as an everyday tool can show children the value of writing is one's life. Katie Wood Ray (2001) described the writing workshop as, "...often filled with so many more possibilities than is a room where students do the writing process"

Emerging Theory of Visual Literacy:

John Debes first coined the term "visual literacy" in 1969 (Fransecky & Debes, 1972). Debes (1969) believed visual literacy referred to seeing (viewing) and simultaneously having other sensory experiences. Later Ausburn and Ausburn (1978) suggested, "Visual literacy can be defined as a group of skills which enable an individual to understand and use visual for intentionally communicating with others" (p. 291). Hortin's (1983) definition of visual literacy is the definition of visual literacy for this case study. Hortin (1983) stated, "Visual

literacy is the ability to understand (read) and use (write) images and to think and learn in terms of images, i.e., to think visually” (p. 99). Teachers implement any strategy, including visualization, to boost struggling readers and increase comprehension. Visualization has roots in the arts and literacy. Teachers frequently have their students visualize the text as they read to make meaning of the words and help increase reading comprehension. NCTE and IRA state that educators should, “challenge students to analyze critically the texts they view and to integrate their visual knowledge with their knowledge of other forms of literacy” (NCTE & IRA, 1996, p. 6). Consequently, there has been interest for the past decade in the role of visualization with regards to literacy.

Conclusion:

Understanding how visualization in the writing process influences struggling learners requires the understanding of several theories. Piaget and Inhelder’s (1969) cognitive development theory and Vygotsky’s (1978) sociocognitive theory serve as the framework upon which the writing workshop is built. Identifying the student’s cognitive developmental stage may provide an understanding of the whole student. This is important when the student expresses his or her ideas verbally about his or her drawings and writings. Linguistic and visual/spatial intelligence, two of the nine multiple intelligences stated in Gardner’s (1983/2004) MI theory, are applied to the writer’s workshop when visualization occurs. The emerging theory of visualization encompasses the ability to make mental imagery, and the act of drawing images serves as a springboard for writing.

Results of inquiry from the fields of brain research, art and cognition, the writing workshop, visual literacy, and literacy and art contributed to the framework of this qualitative case study. Although the available research discusses writing and art from various points of view, none focus on the potential developmental connection between one’s stage of artistic development, writing level, and stage of cognitive development. Also, the available research does not address visualization embedded in the writing process with a systematic method of inquiry. Weaving together multiple theories and related research may help understand how visualization in the writing process may benefit writing instruction.

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